

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY IN THE SURGERY OF RECURRENT LARYNGEAL AND TRACHEAL PAPILLOMATOSIS

Sadykov R.A.

Hayaliev R.Ya.

Azadov B.R.

RSSPMCS named after Academician V.Vakhidov,
RSPCSM, Urgench branch of TMA, Uzbekistan
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Relevance. Recurrent respiratory papillomatosis (RRP) is the most common, as well as the most expensive benign neoplasm of the respiratory tract in the United States. There are reports of the clinical benefits of therapeutic vaccines for patients with RRP. But none of the reports have definitively demonstrated the induction of HPV-specific T cell responses, suggesting that some or all of the clinical benefit caused by this treatment was due to local, non-specific antiviral inflammatory reactions involving type I interferon. To date, at least 50 different treatment methods are known, none of which guarantees a lasting cure. The problem of radical treatment of respiratory papillomatosis still remains unresolved. The use of lasers in papillomatosis surgery is a generally recognized preferred method due to their undoubted advantages over cold instruments. There are not many reports in the literature on the use of laser and photodynamic therapy (PDT) for respiratory papillomatosis, especially in recent years. The use of PDT reduces the aggressiveness of the course of respiratory papillomatosis, in particular papillomatous lesions of the larynx. An analysis of the literature data indicates that the results of surgical treatment of patients with laryngeal and tracheal papillomas cannot be considered satisfactory, there is a need for repeated therapeutic measures, an integral part of which is considered to be high-precision and minimally invasive endoscopic and laser surgery. The aim of our experimental study was to evaluate the effect of semiconductor IR laser radiation followed by PDT on the mucous membrane of the larynx and trachea.

Materials and methods: The advantage of an IR diode laser is the ability to generate radiation in the near-infrared spectrum of 1.36 microns, which penetrates deep enough into biological tissues and can be delivered to the affected area through flexible monofilament optical fibers of arbitrary diameter. We used a Giga laser for research with a maximum power of 15W, light guides with a diameter of 400 mm. The frequency of radiation, as well as the power, can

be varied. For experiments on rabbits, a radiation power of 3W, an effect on an area with a diameter of 3mm, and a pulse duration of 20 milliseconds were used. At the same time, the energy of the laser exposure was 20-30 J. The research was performed in the Laboratory of Experimental Surgery of the State Institution "RSSPMCS named after Acad. V.Vakhidov". Mongrel rabbits and mini pigs were used as experimental animals. 5-aminolevulinic acid was used as a photosensitizer. Light-optical micrographs were obtained using a "DN-300M" microscope coupled with a digital camera and a computer. All micrographs were processed and stored on a computer using Microsoft's Windows 10 pro application programs. The method of exposure consisted in conducting a catheter into the lumen of the trachea according to the method described above. Then the catheter was removed and the trachea, vocal cords and larynx were irradiated with a laser at the specified dosage with a frequency of 1-2 Hz. Laser treatment of the trachea and larynx required 10-15 laser flashes (200-350 joules of radiation).

Results: The conducted studies have allowed a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of the effect of a diode laser in combination with photodynamic therapy (PDT) on the tissues of the larynx and trachea. During the experiments, it was found that the radiation of a diode laser has a significant effect on the deeper layers of the laryngeal and tracheal walls, including cartilage tissue. This effect leads to the development of an inflammatory process, which can further contribute to the excessive growth of connective scar tissue, which is especially important in the context of the prevention of cicatricial strictures of the respiratory tract. In the early stages after laser exposure (in the first 2-3 days), a pronounced inflammatory reaction is observed, which is confirmed by morphological data. In the tissue of the larynx and trachea, neutrophil infiltration, swelling of the submucosal layer, as well as necrotic changes in the epithelium are noted. These morphological changes indicate that laser radiation causes significant cell damage, which leads to activation of the local inflammatory response. It is important to note that at this stage regenerative processes are just beginning to manifest themselves and are characterized by the initial stage of epithelialization, which remains poorly expressed. The use of photodynamic therapy using a photosensitizer (FS) of 5-aminolevulinic acid (5-ALA) and subsequent laser irradiation in the range of 630 nm led to significant changes in the dynamics of the inflammatory process and tissue regeneration. It was found that PDT has a modulating effect on the inflammatory process, delaying the proliferative phase of inflammation. This is manifested in a

decrease in the intensity of granulation tissue growth and a decrease in the degree of scarring. Morphologically, this is expressed in a decrease in the number of inflammatory cells and an acceleration of the epithelialization process, which becomes more active on 5-7 days after exposure. On the 14th day, the tissue regeneration process is almost complete. The epithelial cover is completely restored, and the submucosal layer shows signs of maturation of fibrous tissue, which is a characteristic sign of the completion of reparative processes. Studies have shown that the use of PDT in combination with laser irradiation contributes not only to accelerating tissue healing, but also to reducing the risk of pathological scarring, which is extremely important for maintaining normal respiratory tract function.

Conclusions: In the performed studies, it was found that the use of a diode laser in combination with photodynamic therapy (PDT) has a significant effect on the deep structures of the laryngeal and tracheal walls, including cartilage tissue. Laser radiation causes a pronounced inflammatory reaction in the first 2-3 days after exposure, which is accompanied by neutrophil infiltration, swelling of the submucosal layer and necrotic changes in the epithelium. These processes create conditions for the development of excessive growth of connective scar tissue. The use of PDT using a 5-ALA photosensitizer and laser irradiation in the 630 nm range demonstrated the ability to modulate the inflammatory response, delaying the proliferative phase of inflammation and reducing the intensity of scarring. The combination of a diode laser and PDT with FS 5-ALA is a promising method for the prevention of scarring of laryngeal and tracheal tissues, which can significantly improve clinical outcomes and maintain normal respiratory tract function in patients

